

Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part X. Viscosity Variations during Mutual Coagulations of Positive Ferric Oxide Sol and Colloid Arsenious Sulphide, Manganese Dioxide, and Antimony Sulphide.

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A review of the literature on the subject showed that but little quantitative information is available on the kinetics of the mutual coagulation of oppositely charged colloids, and especially about the corresponding changes of viscosity. It has been shown in previous work (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329 ; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 599 ; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 133) that during the *slow* coagulations of a number of sols due to different electrolytes, the viscosity increases discontinuously, and also that in a number of well ascertained cases (Joshi and Nanjappa, *loc. cit.* ; Joshi and Iyengar, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 555), the above property actually decreased below the initial value. This suggested that the viscosity change is not necessarily a measure of coagulation at any rate in the *slow* region. Since this appeared to be contrary to the current views on the subject, it appeared desirable to examine the validity of the above deduction from the standpoint of a new type of evidence ; to this end, for reasons mentioned already, measurements of viscosity changes during *mutual* coagulations were undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Colloid ferric oxide was prepared by hydrolysing an aqueous solution of about 5 g. of ferric chloride in a litre. It was dialysed against repeated changes of hot water, till the dialysate was free from chlorine. The colloid content was estimated as in Part VII (Joshi and Nanjappa, *loc. cit.*). The arsenious and antimony sulphide

sols were prepared and estimated for their strengths as described in Parts I and II (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11, 337). The manganese dioxide sol was prepared as recommended by Cuy (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 415). The colloid contents per litre of these sols were 1.5 g. Fe_2O_3 , 3 g. As_2S_3 , 2.1 g. MnO_2 and 1.9 g. Sb_2S_3 . The viscosity was measured by Scarpa's method with modifications described previously (Joshi and Vishwanath, *loc. cit.*). The temperature of the thermostat was kept constant at $35^\circ \pm 0.1$. The suction applied was 27 cm. of water, and kept constant within 0.3 mm. This was such that the time of rise and fall for the constant volume of the liquid was approximately the same. Other details of manipulation and precautions have been described in Parts VI-VIII. On repeated measurements with a standard liquid like water at the above temperature the apparatus used was capable of giving an accuracy of 0.15%. Changes in viscosity at least four times as great only are reported.

40 C. c. of the mixture were placed in the Scarpa tube in all the experiments. It contained 20 c. c. of the ferric oxide sol in experiments referred to in Tables I, III and IV. Different volumes of any of the oppositely charged colloid, *viz.*, As_2S_3 , MnO_2 and Sb_2S_3 , were then diluted with such amounts of water that the volume of the diluted sol was always 20 c. c. (*cf.* 2nd column in Tables I-IV). The two sols were allowed to attain the temperature of the thermostat before mixing. Experiments in Table II refer to coagulations when the amount of colloid ferric oxide was varied and that of arsenious sulphide kept constant. Results for η , the viscosity, have been expressed relative to that of water taken as unity, and have been shown graphically in Figs. 1-3. Results quoted in Tables I-IV have been obtained from the corresponding viscosity-time curves. The following abbreviations have been used: η_i = initial viscosity; η_m = first minimum viscosity; η_d is percentage diminution, *i. e.*, $(\eta_m - \eta_i) / \eta_i \times 100$; T_{η_m} is time in minutes corresponding to η_m . Remarks in the last column relate to observations of coagulation or otherwise, as judged by the production of the characteristic turbidity some times accompanied by minute particles of the coagulum. Curve Nos. shown in circles in Figs. 1-3 and in 1st column in Tables I-IV refer to mixtures where coagulation was observed. Viscosity measurements were continued, until the coagulum tended to make the system appreciably heterogeneous, and leave a deposit on the walls of the viscometer.

TABLE I.

Colloid content: (i) 1.5 g. Fe_2O_3 per litre; (ii) 3.0 g. As_2S_3 per litre.

Expt. No.	Composition of the mixture in c. c.			$\eta_{i.}$	$\eta_{m.}$	$\eta_{d.}$	$T\eta_{m.}$	Remarks.
	Fe_2O_3	As_2S_3	Water.					
1	20	+ 20	+ Nil	1.04	1.03	1.25	39	No sensible flocculation in several hr. after mixing.
2	20	+ 16	+ 4	1.07	1.06	—	13	No sensible flocculation in 2 hrs.
3	20	+ 15	+ 5	1.11	1.03	6.5	25	Do
4	20	+ 12	+ 8	1.09	—	—	—	
5	20	+ 10	+ 10	1.06	—	—	—	Coagulation after 54 mins.
6	20	+ 5	+ 15	1.05	1.05	—	16	
7	20	+ 2	+ 18	1.09	—	—	—	
8	20	+ 1	+ 19	1.09	—	—	—	Immediate coagulation after mixing.
9	20	+ 0.5	+ 19.5	1.03	—	—	—	Do

TABLE II (cf. Fig. 1).

Colloid content: (i) 3 g. As_2S_3 per litre; (ii) 1.5 g. Fe_2O_3 per litre.

Curve No.	Composition of the mixture in c. c.			$\eta_{i.}$	$\eta_{d.}$	$\eta_{s.}$	$T\eta_{m.}$	Remarks.
	As_2S_3	Fe_2O_3	Water.					
1	20	+ 18	+ 2	1.06	1.03	2.7	55	No sensible coagulation.
2	20	+ 15	+ 5	1.07	1.03	2.0	21	
3	20	+ 10	+ 10	1.05	1.03	2.2	33	
4	20	+ 5	+ 15	1.08	1.04	4.5	22	
5	20	+ 2	+ 18	1.17	1.15	1.9	16	
6	20	+ 1	+ 19	1.05	1.04	1.1	14	
7	20	+ 0.5	+ 19.5	1.04	1.02	1.8	30	

TABLE III (cf. Fig. 2).

Collid content: (i) 1.5 g. Fe_2O_3 per litre; (ii) 2.1 g. MnO_2 per litre.

Curve No.	Composition of the mixture in c. c.				η_i	η_m	η_h	$T\eta_m$	Remarks.	
	Fe_2O_3	MnO_2	Water	Nil						
1	20	+	20	+	Nil	1.05	1.04	1.0	12	
2	20	+	15	+	5	1.04	1.03	0.4	22	No sensible flocculation in 2 hours.
3	20	+	12	+	8	1.03	1.03	0.4	14	Immediate coagulation.
4	20	+	10	+	10	1.05	1.03	2.2	33	Immediate coagulation.
5	20	+	1	+	19	1.03	1.01	2.1	14	
6	20	+	0.5	+	19.5	1.03	1.01	2.0	39	

TABLE IV (cf. Fig. 3).

Colloid content: (i) 1.5 g. Fe_2O_3 per litre; (ii) 1.9 g. Sb_2S_3 per litre.

Curve No.	Composition of the mixture in c. c.				η_i	η_m	η_h	$T\eta_m$	Remarks.	
	Fe_2O_3	Sb_2S_3	Water	Nil						
1	20	+	10	+	10	1.08	1.05	3.0	13	Coagulation sensible after 5 mins.
2	20	+	6	+	14	1.05	1.04	1.5	14	
3	20	+	5	+	15	1.18	1.10	0.7	21	Coagulation sensible after 50 mins.
4	20	+	4	+	16	1.04	1.02	1.2	13	
5	20	+	2	+	18	1.03	1.03	1.0	29	No sensible coagulation.

DISCUSSION.

Data in Tables I-IV show that the occurrence of mutual coagulation is not produced for all the proportions in which the two oppositely charged colloids are mixed. This agrees with the results of Biltz (cf. Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, p. 478) obtained with mixtures of the As_2S_3 and Fe_2O_3 sols that (a) coagulation was generally favoured when their colloid contents were approximately equal, and that (b) the change was slow to appear and appreciably restricted in bulk when there was a preponderating excess of one of the two constituents. Since in the present experiments the strength

of the As_2S_3 sol is twice as great as that of the Fe_2O_3 sol, it is to be anticipated that coagulation would not be sensible, unless the concentration of the former sol is reduced to half by dilution with water before mixing with the other colloid. The absence of coagulation in experiments recorded in Table II and in Nos 1-4 in Table I, and its appearance from No. 5 onwards is in agreement with the above deduction. It is also seen that as suggested by (b), results in Tables III and IV show that coagulation occurs only for an intermediate range of proportions of the two colloids. In this connection, it is somewhat surprising to note from results in Table I that coagulation was both distinct and quick to appear even though the amount of the As_2S_3 sol was reduced to as low as 0.5 c. c. (and diluted with 19.5 c. c. of water), while that of the Fe_2O_3 sol was 20 c.c.

It is seen from the foregoing results that a decrease of viscosity in the range 0.7 to 6.5% of the initial viscosity occurs in 22 out of 27 coagulations studied, within 16 to 39 minutes (in one, 55) after mixing the colloids. The η -time curves (not shown in fig.) corresponding to experiments No. 4, 5, 7 and 8 in Table I showed that viscosity increased rapidly during these coagulations, and that the initial viscosity diminution was insensible, as observed in numerous instances of *rapid* coagulation reported previously (cf. Parts VI-IX, *loc. cit.*). It would appear however that although the present results confirm the frequent occurrence of an initial fall of viscosity as observed in the considerable number of *slow* coagulations studied previously (*loc. cit.*), more experimental work is needed to elucidate the nature of the micellar and other changes connected with its occurrence. It might be mentioned that the magnitude of the initial fall of viscosity observed in some of these *mutual* coagulations is considerably larger than that observed in *electrolytic* coagulation studied previously. It was also observed (cf. Joshi and Iyengar, *loc. cit.*) that unlike a definite stage in coagulation whose duration is highly influenced by changes in the nature and strength of the coagulator, the time corresponding to the occurrence of the initial fall of viscosity varies but irregularly over not a wide range of time. It is interesting in this connection to observe that (cf. Table II) appreciable values of η_m are observed although there is no sensible coagulation. This suggests that the process (or processes) accessory to this initial diminution of viscosity is nearly as widely occurrent as coagulation itself, and in all probability independent of the latter (*vide infra*).

Fig. 1.

$As_2S_3 + Fe_2O_3$ sols.

Fig. 2.

Mutual coagulation, $Fe_2O_3 + MnO_2$.

Coagulation distinct in curves 3&5.

Fig. 3.

Mutual coagulation, $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Sb}_2\text{S}_3$.

Coagulation distinct in curves 1&5.

An examination of the viscosity-time curves in Figs. 1-3 shows that the last remark is also applicable to viscosity changes η_d produced as a result of mixing the oppositely charged colloids. Moreover, in agreement with results in previous publications (*loc. cit.*) the time variation of the viscosity of the mixed colloids is, in general, *discontinuous*, except when the coagulation is *rapid*. It is also notable that though comparatively more uniform, the viscosity variations are quite appreciable in magnitude even in mixtures where no coagulation could be observed. In experiments No. 7 and 8 corresponding to two successive mixtures in Table I coagulation was observed only in the latter. The corresponding viscosity-time curves (not shown in figure) showed however an essentially similar type, *viz.*, an initial rapid rise to a well marked maximum and a subsequent decrease. Additional evidence in this connection is provided by the series of mixtures to which curves in Fig. 1 refer; these show the occurrence of sensible viscosity variations not accompanied by coagulation (*cf.* other curves in Figs. 2 and 3). *Similar* results, to be published shortly, have been obtained in numerous coagulations

due especially to the use of *non-electrolytes* as coagulators. It might be recalled that quite a considerable part of the current evidence in the literature for the production of coagulation depends upon visual observation of the turbidity and allied changes such as flocculation. Thus defined, coagulation corresponds to but an intermediate region in the series of changes limited on one extreme by the precipitation of the suspended material, and on the other, by the just incipient, perhaps pre-coalescence changes in the micelle initiated on the introduction of but traces of the coagulant. It is to be anticipated therefore that a typical colloid-sensitive property like viscosity should be influenced by changes not sufficiently gross to be noticed under coagulation observed visually by noting turbidity changes. Incidentally, this shows the necessity of following the progress of a given coagulation by more than one of the properties employed generally in these measurements. Such work has been already in progress for some considerable time in these laboratories, and the results will be reported in due course.

SUMMARY.

1. Mixtures of positively charged colloid ferric oxide with varying proportions of negative arsenious sulphide, manganese dioxide and antimony sulphide sols have been studied for mutual coagulation and consequential viscosity changes. The former was usually noticeable for certain intermediate proportions of the two colloids.

2. Sensible viscosity changes were produced even when there was no perceptible coagulation. These changes, in agreement with previous results, showed an *initial fall* of viscosity up to 6.5 per cent. of the initial value, and well marked *discontinuities* on the viscosity-time curves. Both these features tended to disappear in *rapid* coagulations.

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